

Semantic Interpretability in Hierarchical Fuzzy Systems: Creating Semantically Decouplable Hierarchies

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Abstract

Analysing the interpretability of a fuzzy system (either hierarchical or not) involves consideration of its semantic properties and evaluation of its structural complexity. The present paper concentrates on the semantic aspects of interpretability in hierarchical fuzzy systems. Complexity reduction is also considered, but from the perspective of its interaction with semantic preservation. In that sense, the paper shows that only the use of intermediate variables with meaning (interpretable variables) will transform the complexity reduction into a real improvement in interpretability. The paper formalises this idea by introducing the concept of **semantically decouplable hierarchies**. Under the assumption of semantic decouplability, it is shown that the interpretability of the overall hierarchical system can be directly obtained from that of its subsystems. Consequently, the paper defines and measures the interpretability of a **semantically decouplable hierarchical fuzzy system** as the aggregation of the interpretability of its subsystems. Finally, several options will be considered for this aggregation process.

Keywords: Hierarchical fuzzy systems, Interpretability, Semantics, Complexity, Explainable artificial intelligence

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1. Introduction

We live in the age of information and data. Almost every situation, process, and decision is monitored, recorded, and analysed. The prodigious quantity of available data allows the construction of *representations* of these fragments of reality (the situations, processes, or decisions previously mentioned). These representations can be constructed based on rules, concepts, or mathematical equations, and are usually referred to as *models*.

Because a model is a representation of part of reality (we can refer to that part of reality as a *system*), evaluating its quality usually encompasses various aspects that strongly relate to the purpose of the model. In some cases, the model is designed specifically to discover how the system will behave in the presence of a certain stimulus. That type of situation can be properly managed with a model that *simply* replicates the input-output relations of the system, regardless of how it does so. This task is well suited for many modelling tools, including those known as black-box models.

A completely different situation is when we are interested not only in *what* the output will be, but also in *why* it will be this. It is clear that a pure input-output relation is not enough in the latter case. Pieces of knowledge describing or explaining that input-output relation need to be presented. Consequently, the internal structure of the model will be crucial to address this type of situation.

Summarising these two ideas, we can say that the quality of a model can be measured according to (at least) two different dimensions. First, **how accurately the model reproduces** the stimulus/response relation of the modelled system. Second, **how clearly it explains** or describes the underlying mechanism producing (or the knowledge justifying) those input-output relations. While the former question (accuracy) has always been important, the latter one is now attracting significant attention because of the interest in explainable artificial intelligence (XAI). This interest is growing as a result of the increasing influence that *models* have on our lives.

The prevalence of this *algorithmic decision making* has finally generated

some concerns about its ethical and legal aspects. Some of these concerns fall into the category that has been described as the *right to an explanation*. This primarily refers to the right of individuals to be given an explanation for decisions significantly affecting them, for example, a denied loan or high insurance premium.

This question is becoming a legal matter, as shown by the *General Data Protection Regulation* of the European Union, which in Recital 71 states¹:

The data subject should have the right not to be subject to a decision, which may include a measure, evaluating personal aspects relating to him or her which is based solely on automated processing and which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her.

...

In any case, such processing should be subject to suitable safeguards, which should include specific information to the data subject and the right to obtain human intervention, to express his or her point of view, to obtain an explanation of the decision reached after such assessment and to challenge the decision.

Therefore, it is clear that interpretability is currently gaining importance, and **there is a need for modelling tools that can achieve high levels of accuracy and interpretability**. Among the many tools that have been used for modelling, fuzzy systems have demonstrated great performance when evaluated in terms of both aspects. However, it is important to notice that, while accuracy can easily be described and measured (for example, in terms of errors), interpretability evaluation is still an open question: many different concepts and metrics offer a wide repertory of options. Nevertheless, there is at least some agreement about the existence of **two components of interpretability** [16]: those **related to complexity** [33] and **semantics** [3, 31, 17].

¹<https://gdpr-info.eu/recitals/no-71/>

The primary motive for introducing **hierarchical fuzzy systems** (HFSs) was related to the **reduction of structural complexity**. It was an attempt to avoid the curse of dimensionality appearing in conventional (flat) fuzzy rule-based systems (FRBSs). HFSs result in models with fewer rules than their flat counterparts, with each individual rule being simpler (using fewer variables). Interpretability evaluation, in terms of complexity (dimensionality), involves questions about the number of variables, terms, rules, and so on. It is clear then that the interaction between interpretability and HFSs is a question to be considered. Nevertheless, only a few authors have studied it [26, 36, 49].

It is commonly assumed that using an HFS will directly improve interpretability, because of the complexity reduction that it produces. The present paper will focus on this question by analysing the **relation between hierarchy and interpretability, concentrating on the semantic component of interpretability**.

It is clear that hierarchical structure implies a reduction in the number of rules and variables per rule (that is, a dimensionality reduction of the HFS). This reduced dimensionality will reduce the computational complexity of the model. The question is whether this reduced dimensionality ensures a reduction of the *semantic complexity* of the model (the complexity that we should consider when analysing interpretability). The paper will show how **this interpretability improvement will actually occur only with a proper design of the HFS**. As a first approach, we consider that only the use of intermediate variables with meaning will ensure that a real interpretability improvement results from the hierarchical structure. The use of meaningful intermediate variables is not new: several authors have considered it as a tool for an easier design process. However, its influence on interpretability has neither been analysed nor formalised to date.

Assuming the use of intermediate variables with meaning, the overall hierarchical system could be analysed (in terms of interpretability) as the union of several simpler and independent flat subsystems. This approach will allow an independent interpretation of each subsystem, decoupled from the rest of the hierarchy. Consequently, we will work with a smaller number of rules, each of

which will consider a reduced set of variables. The overall interpretation could then be perceived as the union of the individual interpretations. As a result, the overall interpretability measure should be computed as an aggregation of the individual interpretabilities.

Conversely, interpreting an HFS in which intermediate variables have no meaning will require a rule expansion process as a previous step. This process will cancel out the positive effect of the reduced dimensionality of the system.

The introductory part of the paper includes some additional concepts concerning the interpretability of fuzzy systems (Section 2) and HFSs (Section 3). This part is followed by the main contributions of the paper. Section 4 focuses on the analysis of some semantic aspects of interpretability in HFSs that were not previously considered by other authors. Section 5 describes how some of these ideas were implicitly present in some previous work but were neither made explicit nor formalised. The formalisation of interpretability, through the idea of semantically decouplable hierarchies, and the subsequent definitions and theorems, constitute Section 6. Section 7 considers the definition of interpretability measures for HFSs that take account of this new idea and are adapted to it. Finally, the main conclusions of the paper are presented in Section 8.

2. Fuzzy systems interpretability

In the early years of fuzzy systems, the similarity between fuzzy formalism and natural language (being a key aspect of interpretability) was usually considered as a significant design advantage. In fact, that similarity was the foundation for easier knowledge extraction and validation. In recent years, expert knowledge has been substantially replaced by knowledge extracted from data as the primary source [37]. Consequently, the role of interpretability in knowledge extraction is decreasing. At present, its importance is more related to questions such as the previously mentioned *right to an explanation*.

We now consider some definitions of interpretability, as a first step in the analysis of the interpretability of HFSs.

According to Bodenhofer and Bauer [4], interpretability means the *possibility to estimate the system's behaviour by reading and understanding the rule base only*.

Mencar et al. [29] state that interpretability can be assessed by measuring the complexity of making the translation from the model description based on fuzzy logic to the model explanation based on natural language.

If we align the two ideas, the interpretability of a system could be viewed as the possibility to read, understand, and explain the fuzzy system's behaviour from its knowledge base. Consequently, interpretability involves different aspects that are usually grouped into two main categories: semantic and structural interpretability [16, 30].

On the one hand, **semantic interpretability is mostly affected by the similarity between the objects that comprise the fuzzy model** (such as linguistic variables and aggregation operators) **and the concepts** (mental representations) **considered by the human interpreter**. This is somehow connected to the idea of cointension. Cointension was first defined by Zadeh [47] as a qualitative measure of the proximity of the meanings of two objects. It was then considered by Mencar et al. [30] to state that a knowledge base is interpretable if its semantics is cointensive with the knowledge acquired by the user.

On the other hand, **interpretability is not only a matter of the semantics of information, but is also a question of volume**. Limited human capabilities constrain the amount of information that can be stored in short-term memory [32] and processed to capture the *meaning* of the fuzzy system under analysis, which imposes additional restrictions on interpretability. A large number of rules, rules that simultaneously consider many variables, and linguistic variables with large term sets will all negatively affect interpretability. Consequently, structural complexity of the rule-based system should also be taken into account.

Summarising all previous ideas, we can define interpretability as follows:

Definition 1. A fuzzy system is said to be **interpretable** if its reduced complexity and clear semantics make it possible for us to understand and explain its behaviour, by reading it.

Observation 1. Given this definition, it is important to note that the idea of *understanding and explaining the behaviour* could be interpreted in two different ways. In a broad sense, it can refer to understanding and explaining the overall behaviour of the system. In a much more specific sense, it can focus on explaining why a certain output happens in a specific situation. This latter approach is clearly connected to the *right to an explanation*.

Most authors agree on the fact that interpretability is a subjective concept [2] that is difficult to evaluate or maximise. Nevertheless, many interpretability measures are described in the fuzzy literature. Those measures consider quite different aspects and properties of the fuzzy systems, to *compute* a value describing its interpretability.

It has previously been said that interpretability is a question of both semantics and complexity. Consequently, interpretability analysis can be viewed from two different angles: semantic interpretability and structural interpretability [14]. In addition, fuzzy systems are knowledge-based systems with a knowledge base composed of at least two different types of knowledge: linguistic variables and fuzzy rules. This division produces interpretability measures and criteria involving properties that are usually distributed across two levels [2, 50].

When considering semantics, the lower level includes questions such as coverage, normality, and distinguishability of the fuzzy sets [42] or the fuzzy partitions. Properties such as compactness, completeness, consistency, and transparency of rules correspond to the higher level. When complexity is evaluated, questions such as the number of features or the cardinality of the fuzzy partitions define the lower level. The number of rules, or the average number of conditions per rule, is considered at the higher level.

The two axes (semantics/complexity and variables/rules) produce four boxes or categories to group the many proposed measures and indexes. In [16] many

of them are listed, described, and categorised; this shows that most indexes fall into the categories related to complexity measures. This situation probably relates to the fact that those measures are easier to formalise as an objective value. In contrast, some semantic aspects derive from subjective considerations and are hard to formalise. However, there have been several recent attempts to define semantic-based measures that consider the fuzzy partitions [15] and the fuzzy rule base [31, 34]. It is also possible to jointly consider accuracy and interpretability, as well as the balance between them [8, 9]. With recent advances in multiobjective optimisation techniques, a growing number of fuzzy systems consider interpretability and accuracy as the two objectives of a multiobjective design problem [10, 13]. This approach offers the option to achieve good levels of interpretability and accuracy simultaneously, through an automatic design process.

Even considering the large number of papers related to fuzzy systems interpretability, only recently has the question of interpretability been considered in the framework of type-2 FRBSs [1, 20] or HFSs [26, 36, 49].

3. Complexity reduction and hierarchical fuzzy systems

When designing an FRBS to model a complex problem (particularly one with a large number of input variables), designers must overcome what is usually known as the *curse of dimensionality*: the exponential growth in the number of rules as the number of input variables increases. Various options have been considered to manage this challenging problem: the use of compact rule structures [27], sparse rule bases [22], and HFSs, among others. All of these methods will produce a complexity reduction that will, at least apparently, improve interpretability. Obviously, complexity can also be reduced by means of other techniques, such as model reduction, which has been widely considered both in fuzzy and non-fuzzy frameworks [46, 48].

Concentrating now on HFSs, the manner in which the hierarchical structure is created is not unique. The main difference relates to how the components

of the overall system are affected by the hierarchical decomposition. Three main options can be described: decomposition at the level of fuzzy partitions, variables, or rules.

A *hierarchy of rules* produces a priority ordering of the rules. In that structure, the more specific rules have a higher priority, while the priority is lower for more generic rules [45]. A generic rule will only be applied if no specific rule is available. This structure has clear effects from the perspective of output explanation. Interpreting the output involves using the concept of the *level of specificity* of the rules.

Other authors consider multiple partitions per variable, offering different levels of granularity. In this approach, each layer of the hierarchy contains linguistic partitions with different granularity levels, and linguistic rules considering those partitions. This *hierarchy of partitions* is clearly related to the idea of generic/specific rules, where the specificity of the rule relies on the specificity of the partition. The main difference concerns the design process, which in this case is systematic, based either on reduction [18] or expansion [11] methods.

However, the most common approach to HFSs, and the one we will consider in this paper, is that based on the *hierarchy of variables*. It operates by splitting a large system into a cascade of several smaller subsystems. In doing so, the input space is decomposed into several input subspaces with fewer variables, where each input variable is only considered at a certain level of the hierarchy (Figure 1). To involve all variables in the generation of the overall output, the output of each level is treated as one of the inputs to the following level [35].

Both the overall system and the subsystems are FRBSs. To avoid the risk of misinterpretation caused by ambiguous use of the term, the subsystems will be referred to as fuzzy logic subsystems (FLSs). The term FRBS will be applied only to the overall system.

It is clear that the main effect achieved with this hierarchical process is the reduction in the number of rules of the FRBS (that is, a complexity reduction).

Theorem 1. [35] *Let n be the number of system variables, let m be the number*

Figure 1: A hierarchical fuzzy system (serial).

of fuzzy sets for each variable, let L be the number of hierarchical levels, and let n_k be the number of input variables in the k^{th} level, including the output variable of the previous level. Then the total number of rules in a complete rule base is given by

$$T = \sum_{k=1}^L m^{n_k} \quad (1)$$

with

$$n_1 + \sum_{k=2}^L (n_k - 1) = n. \quad (2)$$

Theorem 2. [35] *In the hierarchical system described above, the minimum number of rules is achieved when $n_k = 2$ for all $k = 1, \dots, L$, and this minimum is equal to*

$$T = (n - 1) * m^2. \quad (3)$$

In summary, in an HFS, the number of rules in the overall rule base could be reduced to a linear function of the number of input variables. In a flat FRBS, it is an exponential function of the number of input variables.

The architecture in Figure 1 is usually known as an incremental or serial HFS: each level of the hierarchy contains a single fuzzy subsystem. As an alternative to this hierarchical structure, it is possible to define a so-called parallel or aggregated HFS. In parallel structures, all input variables of a fuzzy system

are received by subsystems located on the first level. Higher levels only take input from the output variables of the previous level (Figure 2).

Figure 2: A hierarchical fuzzy system (parallel).

Cascade fuzzy systems [28, 44] represent a third option, in which all input variables are considered at every level of the hierarchy, in addition to outputs from previous levels. As a consequence, the hierarchy somehow loses the potential to overcome the dimensionality problems. Nevertheless, some recent studies [49] have revisited this structure and defined the concept of stacked hierarchical structure, to improve interpretability.

Finally, it is also possible to modify the serial approach by using output variables from a certain layer in the hierarchy to modify scaling functions (to somehow tune rules) on an upper layer [25], instead of using them as inputs to the upper layer. In this case, the upper layer could be viewed as implementing a parameterised function, where a lower layer defines the values of the parameters (instead of defining an additional input variable). This approach offers an even larger reduction in the number of rules, because it does not add new intermediate variables to the system.

Observation 2. It is clear that these approaches significantly reduce the overall number of rules of the system, as shown in previous theorems. The effect is a

significant complexity reduction. However, does this complexity reduction really improve interpretability?

To date, it appears to be commonly accepted that the complexity reduction directly implies an interpretability improvement. HFSs have been widely used as tools to improve interpretability without really questioning that assumption. The following section will review this idea.

4. The effect of intermediate variables on interpretability

Having considered the complexity reduction produced by the hierarchical approach, we now focus directly on interpretability, and particularly on its semantic component.

First, it is important to observe that some authors have already considered the side-effects of hierarchical approaches on the design process. The design problems caused by the introduction of artificial variables connecting the modules of the hierarchy are mentioned in [39]. The difficulties of designing an HFS in which outputs of intermediate layers have no physical meaning are raised again in [23]. To overcome the problem, the authors use Sugeno rules with only original variables as inputs to intermediate layers. Intermediate variables are only considered at the consequent of the rules. These questions are somehow related to interpretability, but the authors concentrate on design problems without even mentioning interpretability.

As previously stated, the question of interpretability in HFSs has been formally considered only quite recently [36, 49], and has focused only on complexity. It is now time to analyse the existence of possible side-effects of the hierarchy (such as those previously mentioned concerning the design process), affecting interpretability.

To detect these potential side-effects, we compare *feature extraction* and hierarchical approaches, two different methods to reduce complexity in modelling processes.

Complexity reduction through feature extraction (and feature selection) is very common, not only in fuzzy systems but also in almost all modelling techniques. Feature extraction generates a reduced set of new features (usually synthetic variables) from the original set, by means of a mapping function, with the purpose of representing the original data more concisely. However, this process causes a loss of interpretability because, in most (probably all) cases, no explicit and intuitive relation exists between the original and new features. Moreover, only the original features have a *physical* explanation. In that sense, any designer of *interpretable fuzzy systems* will implicitly accept that the set of synthetic variables (extracted features) is less interpretable than the original input variables.

Let us now consider the relationship between feature extraction and HFS design. The analogy is quite simple: intermediate variables in an HFS are ultimately equivalent to extracted features. The only difference is the type of functional relation between original and extracted variables (mostly arithmetical), or between input and intermediate variables (defined in terms of fuzzy rules).

Observation 3. A fuzzy system with a previous feature extraction process will conceptually be equivalent to a parallel two-level HFS, of which the first level comprises the synthesis of the extracted variables, and the second level comprises the fuzzy system itself (Figure 3).

Why do we assume that the use of extracted variables reduces interpretability while the use of hierarchical systems increases it? The most plausible answer is that we assume that intermediate variables in an HFS are *meaningful* because they are generated as the output of an *interpretable fuzzy system*. However, most HFSs use intermediate variables without any conceptual or semantic support; that is, they are synthetic variables.

The problem is that if we consider the many different interpretability metrics available in the literature, to the author's knowledge, the interpretability of the input variables is never considered. If we generate two models with the

Figure 3: Feature extraction as a hierarchical structure.

same number of variables, rules, and linguistic labels, no index will consider how meaningful the input variables are, and consequently no index will distinguish between a model using selected variables and another using extracted (meaningless) variables.

Apparently, the approach best suited to perceiving the differences between selected and extracted variables will be the *logical view index* based on cointension [6, 31]. In this approach, cointension refers to a relation between concepts, such that two concepts are cointensive if they refer to the same objects. Therefore, a knowledge base will be interpretable if its semantics are cointensive with the knowledge that a user builds in his/her mind after reading the knowledge representation, expressed in natural language. We can safely assume that synthetic (extracted) variables will not be cointensive with any knowledge *in the mind of the reader*. Furthermore, there is no clear way to measure how meaningful or meaningless the variables are. In addition, the implementation of this method focuses on internal aspects of the designed model, not on the selection of input variables. Further exploration of cointension, as a way to evaluate the semantic quality of synthetic variables, could be an option to address this problem.

Consequently, to date there is no formal way to assert that a fuzzy system

with selected features is more interpretable than one with extracted variables. However, it is a commonly accepted idea, and it makes sense.

Let us now imagine a system to control the brake of a car: a two-layered HFS with two intermediate variables, u_1 and u_2 , as the inputs to the second layer of the system. This second layer will have quite simple rules with only two inputs. However, how can one interpret the rule

$$\text{If } u_1 \text{ is } \textit{Low} \text{ and } u_2 \text{ is } \textit{Medium} \text{ Then } \textit{Brake} \text{ is } \textit{Soft}, \quad (4)$$

given that the *interpreter* does not know what u_1 and u_2 mean? An isolated interpretation of such a rule seems impossible, so the user will need to analyse the system as a whole. He/she will need to jointly inspect rules on the first and second layers, because this is the only way to understand u_1 and u_2 . Consequently, interpretability analysis should consider the system as a whole. Consequently, its complexity should be revisited and jointly evaluated.

To avoid this situation, we need to use intermediate variables that can be interpreted, and consequently, that allow an independent interpretation of the subsystems making up the hierarchy. As a first step in this process, we will first formalise the concept of interpretable intermediate variables.

Definition 2. We define an **interpretable hierarchy of variables** as any hierarchical decomposition of variables in which every variable (on any layer of the hierarchy) represents a property or a concept related to the problem under analysis, which can be interpreted (understood) by a human.

The idea of an interpretable hierarchy of variables has a certain affinity with the *structure of computational perceptions* described in [40, 41] to construct a *granular linguistic model of a phenomenon*. A computational perception (CP) is the computational model of a unit of meaning about the phenomenon to be modelled. In that sense, it can be related to the variables considered in the previous definition of the interpretable hierarchy of variables. Those variables represent properties or concepts (related to the problem under analysis) that can be interpreted by a human. These perceptions represent units of meaning

about the phenomenon to be modelled. However, the computational perceptions are not exactly linguistic variables. A computational perception, such as *consumption*, can take simple values, such as “the consumption is low”, but also quite complex values, such as “I am afraid that your efficiency of energy consumption has decreased during the last semester”.

In the structure of computational perceptions, the idea of *hierarchy* is not considered by the authors. However, their approach uses different levels of granularity, which can be viewed as a type of hierarchy. Lower-level CPs are aggregated to produce higher-level CPs. This aggregation is performed through aggregation mappings (another component of the proposed architecture). As an example, two CPs, related to temperature and humidity, can be aggregated to produce a CP on comfort. Comfort can then be aggregated with a CP on consumption to produce a CP on efficiency. As presented, it is not defined as a hierarchy of interpretable variables, but it could easily be adapted to that concept.

It is clear that the use of an interpretable hierarchy of variables, or of any other similar concept, such as that of a structure of computational perceptions, will favour the design of more interpretable HFSs.

5. Creating semantically guided hierarchies

To take advantage of complexity reduction, each subsystem of an HFS should be interpretable as a single structure; this requires interpretable intermediate variables. The question then is, is it possible to create a hierarchy with meaningful intermediate variables (that is, an interpretable hierarchy of variables)? The answer is obviously positive, at least in some cases: probably in those cases in which the use of an HFS makes sense. The only need in those cases is to follow a semantics-based design process (that is, a design process guided by the semantic hierarchy of variables). However, it makes sense because the quest for interpretability requires appropriate design processes, in which the meaning of variables plays a role.

As an example of such a hierarchy, we define the structure of an HFS to model the *braking distance* of a car. Three main factors will affect the braking distance: the grip of the road, the braking capability of the car, and its movement. The movement of the car is basically defined by its speed and weight. The effect of the braking system on braking distance could be defined through the condition of the brakes and the wheels. Finally, the grip of the road depends on the asphalt and the weather conditions (for example, rain or ice). We have then generated an interpretable hierarchy of variables. This approach could be represented by a two-layer HFS with four FLSs. The six input variables will be: *Speed*, *Weight*, *Brakes condition*, *Wheels condition*, *Asphalt*, and *Weather conditions*. Three FLSs will integrate these six variables to produce the three intermediate variables (*Car movement*, *Car condition*, and *Road condition*) that will be the inputs to the second-layer FLS that computes the *Braking distance* of the car. Figure 4 illustrates this example and shows how this structure, based on an interpretable hierarchy of variables, can easily be interpreted as four *isolated* FLSs.

Figure 4: A hierarchical structure with meaning.

This is only an example that has been created to illustrate the idea. However, the use of meaningful intermediate variables has already been considered in some previous work. It has been considered mostly as a way to achieve an easier design. Interpretability was not considered, and the use of meaningful variables was implicit in the design process. We will now present some of the relevant previous work. For each one, we will try to explain what, in our view, could be considered as an interpretable hierarchy of variables. Having made the structure explicit, the next section will formalise the related concepts.

In [24], HFSs are applied to the detection of abnormal changes in e-mail traffic behaviour through the fusion of e-mail traffic behaviour measurements (nine variables). The authors consider the use of different HFS architectures to determine the effect that input variable groupings have on the abnormality ratings. They consider three different serial architectures with the same set of nine input variables but different intermediate variables. The three architectures use what can be considered as interpretable hierarchies of variables (different in each case). As an example, the first architecture considers four fuzzy systems on the first layer: *Incoming traffic volume* (2 inputs), *Incoming delays* (3 inputs), *Outgoing traffic volume* (2 inputs), and *Outgoing delays* (3 inputs). The second layer has two fuzzy systems: *Incoming traffic* (having as inputs *Incoming traffic volume* and *Incoming delays*) and *Outgoing traffic* (having as inputs *Outgoing traffic volume* and *Outgoing delays*). The third layer combines *Incoming traffic* and *Outgoing traffic* to obtain the *Abnormality evaluation*. Two other decompositions are considered, still with a parallel architecture with three layers and meaningful intermediate variables.

The three architectures are tested on the same set of examples, producing consistent results but showing small variations, particularly in cases falling in the middle of the abnormality range. According to the authors, the variations are caused by the emphasis placed on particular variables because of the different selections of intermediate variables. This fact should be interpreted as a way to bias the abnormality criteria through the design process, particularly by the selection of intermediate variables.

In [12] a hierarchical fuzzy model comprising five fuzzy systems is constructed, to evaluate the risk of water main failure. The sixteen input variables (risk-of-failure factors) are distributed between 4 systems on the first layer: environmental model (3 inputs), physical model (4 inputs), operational model (4 inputs), and post-failure model (5 inputs). The fifth fuzzy system computes the risk of failure, and takes as input the outputs of the four previous blocks. The model integrates deterioration factors that lead to the failure event (considered in the three first subsystems) and consequence factors that result from the failure event (the fourth subsystem). This structure allows the planning of repair work according to both the probability of failure and the induced damage.

The literature contains more applications of HFSs in which the subsystems could be described as using meaningful intermediate variables. In [7], a customer satisfaction analysis model with a hierarchical rule structure and seven subsystems is described. In [21], the problem of efficiently adjusting road traffic according to real-time changes in road networks is considered. An HFS is applied to itinerary evaluation. Three fuzzy subsystems on the first layer consider independently the aspects related to path, driver, and environment. Their outputs are then integrated by the upper layers of the hierarchy. In [38], a hierarchical fuzzy inference system to model air pollution is built. Its hierarchical structure includes a first layer that considers independently transportation impact, land use impact, and meteorological data. The three components are then integrated by the second layer of the hierarchy. In [19], the problem of diarrhoeal disease prediction is considered, in relation to the improvement of transportation infrastructures in isolated areas. To achieve this, a causal network model with hierarchical structure is built. Obviously, every intermediate variable in this causal model has a real meaning. Finally, the causal model is transformed into a hierarchical fuzzy interpolation system with eight subsystems.

All of these examples show how **a proper use of knowledge in the design process allows the generation of semantically guided hierarchies**. These hierarchies are built based on an interpretable hierarchy of variables. In the following, we formalise some additional concepts and consider the effects of

using such a hierarchy, compared with using a hierarchy without interpretable intermediate variables.

6. Semantically decouplable hierarchies

The central idea will be the design of hierarchies *with meaning*. Having already formalised the concept of an interpretable hierarchy of variables, the semantic coupling of systems that are interconnected through synthetic variables will be considered. Finally, the possibility of a decoupled interpretation of the subsystems of an HFS will be explored.

Definition 3. Two **systems** are said to be **semantically coupled** if they cannot be independently interpreted (that is, if the meaning of one of them can be defined only after the meaning of the other has been established).

Definition 4. A **hierarchical structure** is defined as **semantically decouplable** if it is composed of subsystems that are not semantically coupled.

Consequently, in a semantically decouplable hierarchical structure, the component blocks of the hierarchy, considered independently, describe pieces of information (parts of the overall system) that have meaning by themselves. It is important to notice that this decouplability does not mean complete independence. As parts of a hierarchical structure, the meaning of a block will be affected by the meaning of other blocks. However, it will be possible to achieve a preliminary description with meaning (that could be improved by adding other blocks of the system) without requiring information about other subsystems.

To illustrate this idea, we can consider a rule on the upper layer of the system shown in Fig. 4.

If *Car movement* is *Low* and *Car condition* is *Good*
 and *Road condition* is *Very Good*
Then *Braking distance* is *Very Short*.

The rule has meaning by itself as a single entity. Furthermore, it is clear that the user could gain a deeper knowledge on its meaning by considering the rules defining *Car movement*, *Car condition*, and *Road condition*. In summary, the piece of knowledge is not coupled to other pieces of knowledge, but (being parts of the same hierarchical structure) it is not completely independent from them. This situation contrasts with that of the rule described in Eq. 4, which has no meaning at all by itself.

Given that decoupled does not mean completely independent, we now explore the concept of *semantically decouplable*.

Theorem 3. *An HFS (serial or parallel) can only be semantically decouplable if it is built based on an interpretable hierarchy of variables.*

PROOF. If the HFS is semantically decouplable, each block of the hierarchy should have meaning on its own. To do so, the input and output variables of each of these blocks should also have a meaning, otherwise the block affected by an input or output variable without meaning will itself lack meaning. The overall set of input and output variables of the blocks constitute a hierarchy, including every input and output variable of the system, in addition to any additional intermediate variables. Because all of them have a meaning, the set of variables is an interpretable hierarchy of variables.

Observation 4. Cascade HFSs have been excluded from the theorem because the more complex interconnection between the subsystems of the hierarchy will not ensure that the sets of input, intermediate, and output variables constitute a hierarchy of variables.

The key aspect for the use of HFSs is the reduction of complexity, but it is necessary to analyse the concept of complexity carefully, because it encompasses several different aspects. The next step in our analysis requires us to distinguish between computational complexity and semantic complexity. Both of them are positively affected by any reduction in the number of rules and

variables of the considered system. From the perspective of complexity, a significant improvement is achieved by working with a hierarchical structure in which variables are distributed and subsystems operate with a reduced number of variables and rules. This complexity reduction, although fully effective in computational terms, requires additional analysis from a semantic perspective.

The required computing time is directly related to the number and complexity of the rules; that is, it is related to the number of rules and variables. It will also be affected by other issues, such as the complexity of the various operators; however, these are unrelated to the use of a hierarchical structure.

Observation 5. In a hierarchical structure, the computational complexity (computing time) of each block of the hierarchy is independent of the remainder of the structure, and the overall computational complexity is the sum of each block's complexity.

Consequently, the use of HFSs reduces computational complexity.

Observation 6. If we consider complexity from a semantic point of view, we should consider substructures that are suitable for a semantic analysis (that is, substructures with meaning). If the hierarchy does not produce such substructures, the semantic analysis should be performed on the hierarchy as a whole.

Working on substructures will surely reduce complexity, but what will the situation be if we work on the overall structure?

Theorem 4. *An HFS that is not semantically decouplable will not reduce semantic complexity effectively.*

PROOF. Without loss of generality, we will assume that the system uses the optimal hierarchical architecture that has only two inputs to each FLS; that is, it is the system with maximum reduction in the number of rules.

Let n be the number of system variables, let m_j be the number of fuzzy sets for variable j (including intermediate variables), let L be the number of

hierarchical levels, and let n_k be the number of input variables in the k^{th} FLS. In this case (because $n_k = 2$ for all k), an HFS with n variables and two input variables in each fuzzy system will require $n - 1$ fuzzy subsystems.

Input variables will be represented as x_1, \dots, x_n , and intermediate variables as u_{n+1}, \dots, u_{2n-2} (there are $n - 1$ fuzzy systems, of which $n - 2$ produce intermediate variables as output). The output of the upper FLS will be y (the overall output); we will also represent y as u_{2n-1} .

For each input and intermediate variable, let μ_{ji} be the i th fuzzy set associated with variable j ($j = 1, \dots, 2n - 1$ and $i = 1, \dots, m_j$).

First, we will consider a serial structure (Fig. 1). In this case, there is a single FLS on each layer, so that $L = n - 1$.

Let N_l be the number of rules in FLS_l , and let $N_{l,i}$ be the number of these rules having $\mu_{n+l,i}$ as output membership function (associated with the output variable u_l). Finally, let \hat{N}_l be the number of equivalent expanded rules in FLS_l to compute u_l ; that is, \hat{N}_l is the number of expanded rules in an equivalent flat system using only the actual input variables x_1 to x_{l+1} . $\hat{N}_{l,i}$ will be the number of these (expanded) rules having $\mu_{n+l,i}$ as the output membership function. It is obvious that

$$\hat{N}_l = \sum_{k=1}^{m_{n+l}} \hat{N}_{l,k}, \quad \forall l = 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

With these definitions:

$$\hat{N}_1 = N_1 = m_2 * m_1,$$

$$N_2 = m_3 * m_{n+1},$$

$$\hat{N}_2 = \sum_{i=1}^{m_3} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{n+1}} \hat{N}_{2,k} = \sum_{i=1}^{m_3} \hat{N}_1 = m_3 * \hat{N}_1 = m_3 * m_2 * m_1 = \prod_{j=1}^3 m_j.$$

Considering now the case of any intermediate system FLS_l , its input variables will be x_{l+1} and u_{l-1} , and its output variable will be u_l . The number of rules and expanded rules for this FLS are:

$$N_l = m_{l+1} * m_{n+l-1},$$

$$\hat{N}_l = \sum_{i=1}^{m_{l+1}} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{n+l-1}} \hat{N}_{l-1,k} = \sum_{i=1}^{m_{l+1}} \hat{N}_{l-1} = m_{l+1} * \hat{N}_{l-1} = \prod_{j=1}^{l+1} m_j,$$

which, for the upper layer (FLS_L), because $L = n - 1$, results in

$$N_L = m_n * m_{n+L-1},$$

$$\hat{N}_L = \sum_{i=1}^{m_n} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{n+L-1}} \hat{N}_{L-1,k} = \sum_{i=1}^{m_n} \hat{N}_{L-1} = m_n * \hat{N}_{L-1} = \prod_{j=1}^{L+1} m_j = \prod_{j=1}^n m_j.$$

In addition, the overall number of expanded rules is $\prod_{j=1}^n m_j$, which is identical to that of a complete flat fuzzy system with the same number of input variables (n) and terms per variable (m_j).

We now consider a parallel structure (Fig. 2), in which the number of inputs is a power of 2 (in this case $n = 2^L$). This situation will produce a *pure* parallel structure with L layers, in which every FLS will receive two inputs from the previous layer, and all input variables will enter as inputs to the first layer. If the number of inputs is not a power of 2, some FLSs on upper layers will directly receive input variables. This will produce a mixture between the parallel and the serial structure, which could be analysed as a mixture of this case (parallel with $n = 2^L$) and the previous one (serial).

We will assume that the number of input variables is $n = 2^L$. L is again the number of layers and $n - 1$ the number of FLSs in the hierarchy. Each FLS in the hierarchy will be identified as $FLS_{r,s}$, where $r = 1, \dots, L$ represents the layer, and $s = 1, \dots, \frac{n}{2^r}$ the position in the layer. Because $n = 2^L$, $\frac{n}{2^r} = \frac{2^L}{2^r} = 2^{L-r}$, layer r will contain 2^{L-r} FLSs.

This notation ($FLS_{r,s}$) is slightly different from the one used for serial structures (FLS_l), but there is a relation between r, s , and l :

$$l = \begin{cases} s & \text{if } r = 1 \\ \left(\sum_{p=1}^{r-1} 2^{L-p} \right) + s & \text{if } r \geq 2 \end{cases}$$

The inputs to $FLS_{1,s}$ (first layer) will be x_{2s-1} and x_{2s} , and its output will be u_{n+s} . The inputs to $FLS_{r,s}$ ($r \geq 2$) will be u_{h-1} and u_h , with $h =$

$\left(\sum_{p=0}^{r-2} 2^{L-p}\right) + 2s$, while the output will be u_t , with $t = \left(\sum_{p=0}^{r-1} 2^{L-p}\right) + s$ (for $r = L$, the output will be the overall output y).

In such a situation:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{N}_{1,s} &= N_{1,s} = m_{2s} * m_{2s-1}, \text{ with } s = 1, \dots, \frac{n}{2} \\ N_{2,s} &= m_{h-1} * m_h, \text{ with } h = n + 2s, \text{ and } s = 1, \dots, \frac{n}{2^2} \\ \hat{N}_{2,s} &= \sum_{i=1}^{m_{h-1}} \sum_{k=1}^{m_h} \left(\hat{N}_{1,2s-1,i} \times \hat{N}_{1,2s,k} \right) = \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_{h-1}} \hat{N}_{1,2s-1,i} \right) \times \left(\sum_{k=1}^{m_h} \hat{N}_{1,2s,k} \right) = \hat{N}_{1,2s-1} \times \hat{N}_{1,2s} = \prod_{j=2^{2^2s-3}}^{2^{2^2s}} m_j.\end{aligned}$$

Considering now the case of any intermediate system $FLS_{l,s}$ at position s of layer l ,

$$\begin{aligned}N_{l,s} &= m_{h-1} * m_h, \text{ with } h = \left(\sum_{p=0}^{r-2} 2^{L-p}\right) + 2s, \text{ and } s = 1, \dots, \frac{n}{2^l} \\ \hat{N}_{l,s} &= \sum_{i=1}^{m_{h-1}} \sum_{k=1}^{m_h} \left(\hat{N}_{l-1,2s-1,i} \times \hat{N}_{l-1,2s,k} \right) = \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_{h-1}} \hat{N}_{l-1,2s-1,i} \right) \times \left(\sum_{k=1}^{m_h} \hat{N}_{l-1,2s,k} \right) = \hat{N}_{l-1,2s-1} \times \hat{N}_{l-1,2s} = \prod_{j=2^{l(s-1)+1}}^{2^{ls}} m_j.\end{aligned}$$

For the output layer ($l = L$), composed of a single FLS ($s = 1$), this will result in:

$$\hat{N}_{L,1} = \prod_{j=1}^{2^L} m_j = \prod_{j=1}^n m_j.$$

This can also be represented by \hat{N}_L because the output layer will always have a single FLS (assuming a single-output system).

Again, the overall number of expanded rules is $\hat{N}_L = \prod_{i=j}^n m_j$, which is identical to that of a complete flat fuzzy system with the same number of input variables and terms per variable.

Consequently, an HFS that is not semantically decouplable does not produce any effective reduction of complexity, from the point of view of interpretability.

Its interpretation requires the user to consider the system holistically, without the option of considering the subsystems as independent semantic entities. In fact, we can even find in the literature authors who directly consider transformation into a flat structure as the way to achieve a linguistic interpretation of a hierarchical model [5]:

The linguistic interpretation of the proposed hierarchical model can be performed by using an equivalence transformation that converts this model into one that is non-hierarchical.

As shown in Theorem 4, such a transformation, for a system that should be interpreted as a whole, does not reduce semantic complexity.

Observation 7. The semantic complexity of a fuzzy system relates to the volume of information (number of rules, variables, and so on) to be managed to capture its meaning. In those situations where an HFS is used, it is necessary to evaluate the actual required volume.

Lemma 1. *When the rules of an HFS need to be expanded for interpretation, the actual volume of information to be considered to compute interpretability is not that of the original set of rules (rules of the HFS), but that related to the expanded set of rules (those of the equivalent flat system) in which all variables are interpretable.*

As previously shown, a hierarchy in which intermediate variables have no meaning will require a complete expansion of rules, producing a number of rules identical to that of the equivalent flat fuzzy system. Under these circumstances, it is possible to reach the following conclusion.

Lemma 2. *The use of an HFS will only reduce semantic complexity effectively (compared with its equivalent flat fuzzy system), if it uses (at least some) interpretable intermediate variables.*

7. Measuring interpretability in hierarchical fuzzy systems

We now consider how to measure interpretability in HFSs. According to the previous ideas, the first question to take into account is the interpretability of intermediate variables. This determines whether there will be a need for the expansion of rules (as stated in Lemma 1). In the case of synthetic intermediate variables, expansion is needed. Consequently, interpretability should be measured on the expanded set of rules. It can be performed by applying any of the different metrics mentioned in Section 2. The simplest metric will be that based on the number of rules, which can be computed according to the method considered in the proof of Theorem 4 to obtain \hat{N}_L (either for serial or parallel HFSs). The use of other metrics—for example, the number of variables per rule—will require similar methods to compute the corresponding values for the expanded set of rules.

In this paper, we concentrate on semantically decouplable hierarchies. Because they use interpretable intermediate variables, the interpretation does not require any expansion of rules. This situation provides the conditions to interpret in an incremental manner, considering each FLS in the structure separately. The use of meaningful intermediate variables ensures that every input and output variable for each FLS has a meaning. Consequently, it is possible to read (interpret, understand, or any other similar concept) each FLS as an *independent*, complete, and closed entity. Interpretability analysis will then be transformed into several independent analyses of different subsystems. Each analysis will produce a certain interpretability value associated with one of the subsystems of the hierarchical structure.

The above process will generate K values of interpretability to be aggregated, characterising the K FLSs in the hierarchy. In [36], the authors propose an aggregation through a weighted sum. Each level or layer has an associated weight, and interpretability at each level is computed as an average of the

interpretability measures of all FLSs at that level:

$$I(HFS) = \sum_{r=1}^L \left(l_r \sum_{s=1}^{m_r} I(F_{rs})/m_r \right). \quad (5)$$

$I(x)$ represents a certain interpretability measure applied to system x , L is the number of layers in the HFS, m_r is the number of FLSs on layer r , and F_{rs} denotes the FLS in position s on layer r . According to [36],

$$l_r = \frac{2(L-r+1)}{L(L+1)}, \quad r = 1, \dots, L. \quad (6)$$

This measure is based on the idea that input variables are distributed over the structure according to their influence [35]. In this distribution, the most influential input variables are considered on the first layer, the next most influential on the second layer, and so on. As a result, weights are defined to aggregate over layers, giving a greater importance to lower layers. To do so, weights decrease as we advance in the hierarchy. This could be a good option if it is applied to a situation where the influence of variables matches this distribution. The problem is that this matching is not so clear.

Observation 8. [43] For the HFS in Fig. 1, there is no general conclusion about which inputs are more influential to the system output. That is, in general we cannot impose a preference ordering on the variables.

Furthermore, in parallel HFSs, all input variables are jointly input to the first layer, and there is no connection between the importance of input variables and the importance of layers. The use of weights should be linked to the importance given to lower or higher layers of the hierarchy, but it is not easy to make a decision about which layer or subsystem is the most influential. Some considerations are possible:

Observation 9. [43] In general, the sharper the membership functions corresponding to a variable, the larger the sensitivity function for this variable. This means that, if one wants the perturbation to be enlarged after passing through a system, then more membership functions should be defined for this variable.

Observation 10. [43] In general, the smaller the values of the subsystem, the smaller the sensitivity for its input variables. Therefore, larger values for the conclusion would amplify the perturbation of the variables, whereas smaller values for the conclusion would reduce the perturbation of the variables when it is passed through the fuzzy system.

Consequently, the influence on the output of the different levels of the hierarchy depends on the specific system under analysis. Therefore, it seems quite difficult to establish weights for the layers unambiguously, particularly for parallel HFSs.

If the idea of weighted sums is discarded as a consequence of the difficulty of determining the weights, what else can be used for aggregation?

The simplest approach is to focus on interpretability in the same way as in other properties, such as robustness and safety, where:

A chain is only as strong as its weakest link.

We can then say that an HFS will only be as interpretable as the least interpretable of its component FLSs. In terms of the usual interpretability measures in the range $[0, 1]$, with 0 being the minimum interpretability, this corresponds to:

$$I(HFS) = \min_{r,s} I(F_{rs}). \quad (7)$$

Having discarded the weighted sum between layers (as a consequence of the difficult interpretation and setting of the weights), Eq. 5 also considers the average to aggregate interpretability inside layers. It is interesting to notice that average (Eq. 5) and minimum (Eq. 7) are two operators that can be generalised through the ordered weighted average operator (OWA). It would be quite easy to generalise these two options by means of an OWA operator aggregating at the level of FLSs located on a layer (intra-layer aggregation).

That option will produce a *layer interpretability* defined as:

$$I(l_r) = h_1(I(F_{r1}), \dots, I(F_{rm_r})),$$

where h_1 is an OWA operator including, as two options,

$$I(l_r) = \sum_{s=1}^{m_r} I(F_{rs})/m_r, \text{ and}$$

$$I(l_r) = \min_{s=1..m_r} I(F_{rs}).$$

Because no clear decision can be taken about the different influence of the layers, the inter-layer aggregation will not consider the layer position. Transposing the previous ideas to aggregate interpretability of different layers, it is possible to reproduce the same concepts as those used inside a layer. The options will then be the average, minimum, or OWA (generalising the two previous functions).

The use of the average at the level of layers, as well as inside the layers, will produce a modified version of Eq. 5:

$$I(HFS) = \sum_{r=1}^L \left(\frac{1}{L} \sum_{s=1}^{m_r} I(F_{rs})/m_r \right) = \sum_{r=1}^L \sum_{s=1}^{m_r} \left(\frac{I(F_{rs})}{L \times m_r} \right), \quad (8)$$

where L is the number of layers in the hierarchy and m_r is the number of FLSs on layer r .

The use of the minimum to aggregate, at both intra-layer and inter-layer levels, produces the previously defined Eq. 7:

$$I(HFS) = \min_{r=1..L} \left(\min_{s=1..m_r} I(F_{rs}) \right) = \min_{r,s} I(F_{rs}).$$

Finally, the use of an OWA to aggregate layers (h_2), which could differ from that used inside the layers (h_1), produces the most general expression:

$$I(HFS) = h_2(I(l_1), \dots, I(l_L)) = h_2(h_1(I(F_{11}), \dots), \dots, h_1(I(F_{L1}), \dots)). \quad (9)$$

This final version includes all previous options except Eq. 5, because the weighted sum, not based on ordering, cannot be described by means of an OWA.

Eq. 9 offers the opportunity to configure a wide variety of interpretability measures to be applied to semantically decouplable hierarchies. Non-decouplable

hierarchies will be evaluated through a rule expansion process that will produce the equivalent flat system to be evaluated.

In summary, interpretability evaluation of an HFS will require three steps. As a first step, interpretability of intermediate variables should be checked. Any meaningless intermediate variable should then be removed through a rule expansion process. The result will be either a flat system or a semantically decouplable hierarchy. Second, interpretability of the overall flat system or the FLSs making up the hierarchy should be evaluated. Third, the interpretability of the FLSs should be aggregated through any of the possible options offered by Eq. 9. If the rule expansion has produced a single flat system, the third step will not take place.

8. Conclusions

Fuzzy systems are a powerful modelling tool, well adapted to achieve both accuracy and interpretability. Interpretability is somehow affected by complexity, and HFSs have demonstrated an ability to reduce the number of rules needed by a fuzzy system. This situation has usually been considered as a way to improve interpretability, but this idea should be carefully considered. While the obtained reduction is clear from the perspective of computational complexity, semantic complexity reduction requires further analysis.

The manner in which a hierarchy is created will affect how its semantic complexity is reduced. In fact, the use of synthetic intermediate variables (having no meaning) will seriously compromise the semantic analysis of the system. It is possible to define design processes in which the intermediate variables represent properties of the considered problem, and therefore are interpretable in that sense. This type of intermediate variable will allow a decoupled analysis of the hierarchical system. In that case, the reduction of complexity will be effective not only from a computational perspective but also from a semantic one.

In summary, the use of a hierarchical structure only improves interpretability when it provides the capability for decoupling the overall system into a family

of simpler subsystems *that can be interpreted independently*. Moreover, this is only possible *when intermediate variables are meaningful* from the perspective of interpretation (that is, when a semantically decouplable hierarchy is used). Otherwise, using a hierarchical structure is not significantly different from the use of feature extraction techniques.

The use of synthetic features as intermediate variables, regardless of how those features were generated (either with fuzzy rules or with any other mapping), avoids decoupling and consequently prevents a proper interpretation of subsystems as independent entities. In fact, interpreting hierarchical systems that include intermediate variables without meaning requires an expansion of rules (to hide the uninterpretable variables). In the case of a system in which no intermediate variable has meaning, this expansion will produce a number of rules identical to that of the equivalent flat fuzzy system. Consequently, no interpretability improvement will be achieved in this situation.

These ideas consider the effect of intermediate variables on interpretability. Assuming the use of a semantically decouplable hierarchy, the hierarchical structure can be decoupled into smaller flat systems independently interpreted. In this case, interpretability evaluation reduces to aggregating the interpretability of subsystems. For that situation, various aggregation procedures have been defined, to obtain an overall evaluation of interpretability. In any other case, interpretability analysis requires the HFS to be expanded until any synthetic variable is removed; only then will it be possible to measure the interpretability of the system.

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